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REVIEW

The stability of graphene oxide (GO) nanofiltration (NF) membrane in aqueous environment: Progress and challenges

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Recently, advanced membranes based on 2D material of graphene oxide (GO) for NF have drawn great attentions due to their striking, dramatic separation performances which are much higher than traditional membranes. However, stability, which is a precondition for practical applications, has become the bottleneck of the GO membranes for water treatment. Fortunately, the stability of GO membranes in water has received significant attentions, and many fruitful efforts have been devoted to solve this problem most recently. It is therefore critical to update the broader scientific community on the important advances in this interdisciplinary field. Herein, we review recent progress in improving the stability of GO membranes in water. Fundamental issues, including the origin of the instability of GO membranes in water, and influences of the chemical properties of GO itself on the stability of the resultant membranes have been discussed. We also explore the diverse structural design and surface/interface engineering strategies for improving the stability of GO membranes in water, including the introduction of hydrogen bonding or intermolecular interaction via insertion of polyelectrolytes, cross-linking by molecules or ions, or blending of graphene-based materials, as well as improving the interaction between GO selective layers and substrates. The existing challenges and a forward-looking perspective are also discussed, suggesting directions to design GO and other 2D material-based membranes with outstanding stability and high separation performance for practical applications.

1. Introduction

A nanofiltration (NF) membrane is a barrier with well-defined nano-size pores and surface properties which can realize the selective transmission of solute with low molecular weight and low valence ions while blocks other species.¹⁻⁴ NF membranes have been widely used for wastewater treatment, pure water production, and other industrial productions.³⁻⁹ An ideal NF membrane for water treatment should have high water flux while maintain required rejection rate under relative low pressure. According to the classical hydrodynamics theory described by the Hagen-Poiseuille Equation¹⁰

$$J = \frac{\epsilon r_p^2 \Delta p}{8 \mu L} \quad (1)$$

Where J is the permeation flux, ϵ is the surface porosity, r_p is the effective pore radius, Δp is the hydraulic pressure difference, μ is the liquid viscosity, and L is the membrane thickness. According to the equation, to obtain high permeation flux, the selective layer of a NF membrane should be as thin as possible.

Moreover, to realize the effective rejection of certain small organic molecules or high valence ions, the selective layer should have precisely adjustable nano pores or channels.

Recently, 2D material of graphene oxide (GO) have drawn great attentions due to its great advantages on preparation of advanced NF membranes.¹¹⁻¹⁹ On the one hand, the monolayer GO nanosheets with thickness less than 1nm can form ultrathin selective layer on many substrates *via* filtration, self-assembly,^{20, 21} blade coating, spray, spin coating, print, and shear alignment²². On the other hand, the nano channels in the GO selective layer can be precisely modulated by adjusting the interlayer spacing among GO layer.²³⁻²⁷ The nanochannels in ultrathin selective layer, as well as nano pores on GO sheets, can endow the GO-based NF membrane with ultrahigh water permeation flux that is orders of magnitude higher than traditional polymer-based NF membranes.²⁸⁻³¹ The precisely adjustable nano channels of the GO-based selective layer can realize precise molecular sieving as needed.^{30, 32-34}

Until now, a series of GO NF membranes with excellent performances have been prepared *via* various ingenious strategies, and scale-up of these membranes to large-areas has also been overcome²², which seems that the industrial application prospect of GO NF is increasing. However, as far as we know, the application of GO NF membranes remains still in laboratory or pilot-plant scale, without industrialization. One of the biggest stumbling blocks is the instability of GO membranes in water. Without long-term stability in water, the industrialized application of GO membranes is merely a castle in the air.

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Fig.1 (A) Schematic illustration of d-spacings of graphite, dry GO, and GO soaked in water.³⁵ (B) XRD spectra of a GO membrane in oven-dried, wetted, and air-dried conditions.³⁵ A and B reprinted with permission from ref. 35.

Therefore, the stability of GO NF membranes in water has received significant attentions most recently, and many fruitful efforts have been devoted to solve this problem. It is therefore critical to update the broader scientific community on the important advances in this interdisciplinary field.

Herein, we review recent progress in improving the stability of GO membranes in water (**Scheme 1**). Fundamental issues, including the origin of the instability of GO membranes in water, and influences of the chemical properties of GO itself on the stability of the resultant membranes have been discussed. We also explore the diverse structural design and surface/interface engineering strategies for improving the stability of GO membranes in water, including the introduction of hydrogen bonding or intermolecular interaction via insertion of polyelectrolytes, cross-linking by molecules or ions, or blending of graphene-based materials, as well as improving the interaction between GO layers and substrates. The existing challenges and a forward-looking perspective are also discussed, suggesting directions to design GO and other 2D material-based membranes with outstanding stability and high separation performance for practical applications.

Scheme 1 The strategies for improving the stability of GO membrane in aqueous environment.

2. The origin of the instability of neat GO membranes in aqueous environment

It is well known that there are many hydrophilic oxygenated functional groups in GO sheets, and these highly hydrophilic groups attract water molecules into the interlayer space of the GO membrane, hydrating the GO sheets and increase the interlayer space (**Fig.1**).^{35, 36} The hydration as well as the electrostatic repulsion generated by negative-charged oxygen-

containing groups leads to the swelling of the GO membrane in water, and the swelling will finally overcome the Van der Waals attraction or hydrogen bonding that holds the GO sheets together, leading to the disintegration of GO membranes.³⁷ Note that the high or low pH value will increase the electrostatic repulsion of GO sheets, further aggravating the instability of the GO membrane in water.³⁸ Moreover, some cation in water can also affect the structural instability of GO membranes. For example, the GO membrane structure can be disrupted by Na⁺ (**Fig.2**),^{39, 40} while the stability of the GO membrane can be improved by Al³⁺.³⁷

Another stability problem of the GO membrane is related to the substrates. The mechanical strength of thin GO membrane is not high enough for application, so porous substrates are usually needed to support the GO membrane.⁴¹ If the interaction between the GO membrane and the substrate is not high enough, the GO membrane will be easily peeled off. Besides, the drying-related shrinkage of GO membrane on rigid substrates such as ceramic membrane will produces enormous tensile stress in the GO membrane and leads to defects.⁴²

Fig.2 The cation-dependent laminar structure of GO membranes. (A) Impact of the hydrated radius of cations on the d-spacing of GO membranes directly after immersion.³⁹ (B) The GO membrane structure after long exposure to electrolyte solutions.³⁹ A and B reprinted with permission from ref. 39.

3. Strategies for improving the stability of GO membranes in water

The stability of GO membranes in water is a precondition for the practical application. So far, many efforts have been devoted to solve this problem most, and some effective strategies have been developed. For example, the stability of GO membranes in water can be improved via covalent cross-linking, non-covalent cross-linking, and protective coating.⁴³⁻⁴⁷

3.1 Improving the stability of the GO membrane itself

3.1.1 Covalent cross-linking

One of the instability problems of the GO membrane is the disintegration or re-dispersion of GO nanosheets in water. Covalent cross-linking is an effective strategy to solve this problem. The functional groups such as carboxyl groups and hydroxyl groups on GO nanosheets provide convenient sites for covalent cross-linking with many kinds of cross-linking agent. Mi et al. prepared GO membrane cross-linked by 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride via covalent reaction between carboxyl groups and acyl chloride, and they found that the cross-linking effectively provided the GO membrane with necessary stability to overcome its inherent dispensability in water environment (**Fig.3A**).⁴⁸ Due to the covalent reaction between amino groups and carboxyl groups on GO nanosheets, molecules or nanoparticles (NPs) with two or more amino groups have also been utilized as cross-linking agents to improve stability of the GO membrane in water (**Fig.3B**).⁴⁹⁻⁶⁶

Fig.3 (A) Schematic illustration of fabrication of GO membrane via layer-by-layer deposition of GO nanosheets, which were cross-linked by 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride, on a polydopamine-coated polysulfone support.⁴⁸ (B) Stability of GO/BPEI membranes in aqueous solution: (a) stability after sonication treatment, (b) stability in acid-base solutions, (c, d) SEM images of membranes after sonication for 30 min at pH 7, (e) mechanism of stabilization of the GO/BPEI membrane at different pH values.⁵¹ A and B reprinted with permission from ref. 48 and ref.51, respectively.

Besides, glutaraldehyde⁶⁷ and 1-allyl-3-vinylimidazolium chloride⁶⁸ have also been utilized as cross-link agent to improve the stability of the GO membrane in water. Although the covalent cross-linking can endow the GO membranes with enough stability in water, the excessive cross-linking will disturb and block water transport within GO nanochannels, leading to the decrease of the water flux of the membrane. So, how to improve the stability of the GO membrane in water, while keep or improve the water permeation flux is still a challenge. An effective strategy is to adjust the d-spacing via changing the chain length of the cross-linking agent, which can increase the water flux to some extent (**Fig.4 A and B**).^{49, 58} Another method is to incorporate some NPs decorated with cross-linking groups. These NPs can not only act as cross-linking agents, but also adjust the interlayer spacing to increase the water flux (**Fig.4 C**).^{61, 64} Besides organic molecule, metal ions (Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , La^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , etc.) can also act as cross-linking agents to improve the stability of GO membrane in water (**Fig.5 A and B**).^{37, 69-73} This is because that the GO nanosheets can be cross-linked by multivalent cationic metal *via* formation of coordination bond. These above-mentioned strategies can effectively improve the water permeation flux, but the swell is still obvious, which may result in the decrease of rejection rate.

In fact, the instability of GO membrane in water is refer to not only the disintegration, but also the swelling that is often ignored. Swelling (without disintegration) can lead to the unstable separation performance (rejection rate). Therefore, restraining swelling is also important to solve the instability of the GO membrane in water. Most recently, Jin et al. reported a molecular bridge strategy, in which an interlaminar short-chain molecular bridge generates a robust GO laminate that resists the tendency to swell, while an interfacial long-chain molecular bridge adheres to GO laminate onto a porous substrate to increase the mechanical strength to the membrane (**Fig.6**).⁶³ By rationally creating and tuning the molecular bridges, the stabilized GO membranes exhibit outstanding durability in harsh operating conditions, such as cross-flow, high-pressure, and long-term filtration.⁶³ Besides, this strategy is universal for various porous substrates such as ceramics, nylon and mixed-cellulose acetate. Moreover, this strategy is also scalable. This versatile approach will open new opportunities for GO membranes used in aqueous environments.⁶³

In brief, amine based molecules can give the stable membrane structure because the GO nanosheets can effectively cross-linked via covalent reaction. However, excessive cross-linking will disturb and block water transport within GO nanochannels, leading to the decrease of the water flux of the membrane. Therefore, endowing the GO NF membrane with excellent stability while keeping the high permeation flux and precise separation performance of the membrane are very important.

3.1.2 Non-covalent cross-linking

Besides covalent cross-linking, non-covalent cross-linking via the Van der Waals force, hydrophobic interaction, π - π interaction, electrostatic and hydrogen bonding interactions

Fig.4 (A) Cross-linking with diamine monomers to prepare GO membranes with varying d-spacing.⁴⁹ (a) Structural diagram of GO and three composite graphene oxide-framework (GOF) membranes (GO-EDA, GO-BDA, and GO-PPD). Each GOF was produced by cross-linking GO with a diamine monomer (EDA, BDA, or PPD). (b) XRD patterns of GO and GOF membrane at dry and wet states, respectively. (B) pH-responsive d-spacing of graphene-based stable pH-responsive membranes (GPMs).⁵⁸ (a) permeate flux of the GPM prepared from GO and the linear PEI (denoted as ML) or the branched PEI (denoted as MB) in the pH range from 3 to 11, respectively, (b) permeate flux of MB and ML when the pH shifted from 11 to 3 and back to 11 for four cycles, (c) XRD spectra of MB and ML, (d) film thickness of MB and ML at different pH values, (e) schematic of potential conformation change of GPM at pH 3 and 11. (C) $\text{NH}_2\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ regulated GO membrane with well-defined laminar nanochannels.⁶⁴ (a) mechanisms of transport process of GO and $\text{GO}/\text{NH}_2\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ membrane, (b) effect of operating pressure on water flux of GO and $\text{GO}/\text{NH}_2\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-8}$ membranes. A, B, and C were reprinted with permission from ref. 49, ref. 58, and ref. 64, respectively. GOF:

Fig.5 (A) GO membranes obtained from Teflon and porous anodized aluminium oxide (AAO) filters have different stability in water.³⁷ (B) Variation of Al-GO and Ca-GO membrane stability with cation quantity in 1M NaCl solution.⁶⁹ A and B were reprinted with permission from ref. 37 and ref. 69, respectively.

Fig.6 (A) Schematic illustration for stabilizing a GO membrane through hierarchical interlaminar short-chain and interfacial long-chain molecular bridges. (B) Anti-swelling capabilities of interlaminar short-chain molecular-bridged GO membranes. (a) XRD patterns (left) of pristine GO and EDA-, PPD-, and PDA bridged GO membranes (color coded). (b) Operation time dependence of water permeance and rejection of pristine GO and EDA-, PPD-, and PDA-bridged GO membranes. (c) Relative variation ratios of water permeance and rejection of pristine GO and EDA-, PPD-, and PDA-bridged GO membranes. A and B were reprinted with permission from ref. 63.

Fig. 7 (A) Schematic illustration of the fabrication strategy and mechanism of the partially reduced graphene oxide (prGO)-doped GO membranes with high stability in aqueous solutions and controllable lamellar spacing.⁷⁴ (a, b) The GO sheets with plentiful oxidation regions (a) are partially reduced to the prGO sheets (b). (c, d) The pure GO membranes have large inter layer spacing d_1 (c) and more oxidation groups on lamellar sheets, leading to stronger repulsive hydration force making GO membranes disintegrate in aqueous solutions (d). (e, f) The prGO-doped membranes have closer interlayer spacing d_2 that creates stronger π - π attraction between GO sheets (e) and a weak repulsive hydration force to keep GO membranes stable in aqueous solutions (f). (B) Stability of GO@Teflon membranes in water, acid, and base solutions.⁷⁴ (a, b) GO@Teflon membranes prepared with 0 wt % prGO. (c, d) GO@Teflon membranes doped with 50 wt % prGO. A and B were reprinted with permission from ref. 74.

has been also utilized to improve the stability of the GO NF membranes in water.

Incorporation of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) or partial reduction of GO membranes can effectively alleviate the swelling of GO membranes, making the GO membranes stable in water. This is because that the partial reduced GO nanosheets can provide enough Van der Waals force (π - π stacking) and hydrophobic interaction to overcome the repulsive hydration and electrostatic repulsion between adjacent negatively charged GO layers. It has been reported that rGO NF membranes exhibit excellent stability in water.^{31, 75, 76} However, narrowed interlayer space between the rGO layer caused by the reduction, as well as the hydrophobic nature of the rGO, significantly decrease the water permeation flux of the resultant membranes. Utilization of partially reduced GO to fabricate GO/rGO composite NF membranes is an effective strategy to minish the decrease of water flux (Fig. 7).^{38, 74, 77-81} The partially reduced GO can lead to weakened repulsive hydration and enhanced π - π attraction in GO NF membranes, while the hydrophilic GO can provide water permeation channels with enough interlayer space. Based on GO and rGO, Morelos-Gomez et al. proposed an easy, scalable, low-energy and environmentally friendly spray-coating deposition method to fabricate GO/rGO NF membrane.⁷⁷ Due to the synergistic effect of GO and rGO, as well as the distinct method, the resultant GO/rGO membrane possesses enhanced shear resistance, good filtration and chlorine resistance, making this

kind of membrane attractive for prolong use with chemical endurance.⁷⁷

Since the rGO plays very important roles, the detailed influence of reduction degree of GO or the additive amount of rGO on the performance of the resultant membrane should be investigated. By controlling the content of oxidized groups via changing reducing condition, Chu et al. prepared GO/rGO membranes with different lamellar distances, and studied the influence of lamellar distance on the stability of the obtained GO/rGO membrane (Fig. 8). The authors provided a critical lamellar distance that varies in aqueous solutions depending on pH values, and found that if the lamellar distance is less than the critical value, the membrane could keep physically stable and remain good water permeation performance in water for a long time.³⁸ Ren et al. found that weak reduction increased the number of pristine graphitic sp^2 domains in rGO nanosheets while keeping the large interlayer spacing of the GO membranes in most regions at the same time, endowing the resultant membrane with better structural stability and separation performance than GO membranes in acid and alkali environments.⁷⁸

Although incorporation of rGO can improve the stability of GO membranes in water, the rGO incorporated in GO membranes will decrease channel sizes and solvation levels due to the loss of oxygen sites, which may cause barriers for water entering and subsequent transport.⁸² Incorporation of other nanomaterials can increase the d-spacing, thus improve the

Fig. 8 (A) Schematic illustration of effect of lamellar distances on the stability of graphene-based membranes.³⁸ (a) GO membrane that was stacked by pristine GO nanosheets with plenty of oxidized groups is unstable in aqueous solution due to the weak π - π attraction force (F_{π}) and the strong hydration repulsive force (F_H). (b) Facilely reduced graphene oxide (FRGO) membrane that was stacked by the FRGO nanosheets with mild reduction is still unstable in aqueous solution although the F_{π} increases to some extent. (c) FRGO membrane that was stacked by the FRGO nanosheets with large reduction degree is stable in aqueous solution due to the increased F_{π} and decreased F_H . (d) Schematic relationship between the lamellar distance and the ΔF ($\Delta F = F_{\pi} - F_H$) inside the graphene-based membranes. The gray region represents the unstable membranes, while the yellow region stands for the stable ones. The red dashed line represents the critical lamellar distance (d_c). (B) Systematic results on stability of graphene-based membranes with diverse oxidized-group-supported lamellar distances in acidic solutions (pH 1.0) (a), water (pH 6.6) (b), and basic solutions (pH 11.2) (c) by stirring test during different time periods.³⁸ The black circles mean that the membranes are intact, and the red crosses mean that the membranes are broken at the observation moment. The blue dotted lines mark the estimated critical lamellar distance of graphene-based membranes for different situations. The yellow regions represent the range of lamellar distances of stable graphene-based membranes in aqueous solutions, while the gray regions represent the unstable ones. A and B were reprinted with permission from ref. 38.

water flux while keep enough stability in water. So far, many kinds of nanomaterials such as CNT,⁸³⁻⁸⁵ Fe_3O_4 ,⁸⁶ TiO_2 ,⁸⁶ UiO-66,⁸⁶ attapulgite,⁸⁷ niobate nanosheet,⁸⁸ MoS_2 ,⁸⁹ boron nitride nanosheet,⁹⁰ and MXene⁹¹ have been utilized to improve the stability and permeation of GO membrane. However, the rejection property of the GO membranes incorporated with nanomaterials was reduced significantly due to the fact that it was difficult to regulate the intercalating materials and achieve evenly-distributed deposition between interlayers.^{86, 92} Compared with incorporated nanomaterials, polymers can be better distributed on GO nanosheets, thus can significantly decrease the disarranged laminar structure and larger interlayer spacing, realizing the improved water flux and dye rejection.^{92, 93} Most importantly, the entanglement of polymer chains grafted on GO nanosheets can provide enough

interaction to keep the structural stability of the GO membrane in water. Xu et al. reported an effective strategy to prepare highly stable GO NF membrane by intercalating ionic polymers rich in benzene and cationic imidazolium (or anionic sulfonic acid) moieties (**Fig. 9A**).⁸² The incorporated ionic polymers can non-covalently cross-link neighbouring GO nanosheets via π - π , electrostatic and hydrogen bonding interactions. Li et al. reported a strategy to improve the structural stability and water permeance of GO membrane by grafting of polysulfone onto GO nanosheets (**Fig. 9B**).⁹² Wang et al. prepared amphiphilic Janus GO nanosheets by modification of one side of the GO nanosheets with dodecylamine, and found that the Janus GO nanosheets can strengthening interactions among neighbouring GO nanosheets and thus preventing structural disintegration in water (**Fig. 9C**).⁹⁴

Fig.9 (A) Non-covalent cross-linking to boost the stability of GO membrane.⁸² (a) Illustration of non-crosslinking GO membranes via π - π electrostatic and hydrogen bonding interactions. (b) The models used for calculating the binding energies between 1m cations on the 1m-PPO and epoxy on the GO as well as between sulfonic acid on the S-PPO and GO on the GO. (c) Stability of dry and solvated GO, C-GO and A-GO membranes in water, respectively. (d) Permeances and rejection of EB dye solutions of dry and solvated GO, C-GO and A-GO membranes, respectively. (B) Polysulfone-grafted GO membrane.⁹² (a) Schematic diagram of GO-g-PSf composite membrane fabrication. (b) Photographs of GO composite membrane (M-GO-0.4, left) and GO-g-PSf composite membrane (M-GP-0.4, right) at different times of the ultrasonic irradiation experiment. CMPSF: chloromethylated polysulfone. (C) Janus GO (JGO)-doped composite membranes.⁹⁴ (a) Illustration of molecular transport through the nanochannel constructed in (a) GO lamellar membranes and (b) JGO-doped composite membranes. (b) Membranes with different JGO contents at pH = 2, pH = 6.5, and pH = 12 after being soaked in water for 2 h with mechanical agitation. A, B and C were reprinted with permission from ref. 82, ref. 92, ref. 94.

3.1.3 Protective coating

As has been mentioned, cross-linking agents in GO membrane will disturb and block water transport, resulting in the decrease

of water flux. An alternative is to utilize protective coating. Different from cross-linking agents in the channels of GO NF membrane, the protective layer is on the outer surface of the GO membrane. Thus, the transport channels of GO NF

Fig. 10 (A) Schematic of the water–organic separation process using the synergistic effect of a hydrophilic polymer and GO laminates.⁹⁵ (a) Schematic of the water–organic separation process using the synergistic effect of a hydrophilic polymer and GO laminates. (b) Schematic of the nanoscratch test. (c) Scratch depth–displacement curve of the CS@GO membrane. (d) FESEM images of the interfacial failure of the GO laminates and the CS@GO membranes. (e) Load–displacement curve of the CS@GO membrane. (B) Stable CNT/rGO/PAN membrane.⁹⁶ (a) The distinct advantages of the CNT/rGO/PAN membrane. (b) Exposure of the 20–40CNT_{29.5}/rGO₄₈/PAN membrane to strong ultrasound generated by an ultrasonic cell crusher (270 w). (c) 20–40CNT_{29.5}/rGO₄₈/PAN membrane after exposure for 5 min. (d) Back flushing of the 20–40CNT_{10.0}/rGO₄₈/PAN membrane at a transmembrane pressure difference of 0.1 MPa. (C) GO membrane with sandwich structure.⁹⁷ (a) Schematic illustration of the sandwich structure of GO composite membrane. (b) Digital image of a free-standing TiO₂ intercalated PA 6@GO(120)@PA6 membrane. (c) The cross-sectional SEM image of PA6@GO (120)@PA6 membrane. (d) The top view SEM image of PA6@GO(120)@PA6 membrane. (e) The top view SEM image of TiO₂ intercalated PA6@GO(120)@PA6 membrane. (D) Sandwich GO (SGO) hollow fiber membranes.⁹⁸ (a) The schematic of preparation of SGO hollow fiber membranes. (b and c) The schematics of GO membranes with increased interlayer spacing and SGO membranes with confined interlayer spacing in water. SEM images of (d and e) the GO/PES hollow fiber membrane and (f–h) the SGO-W/PES hollow fiber membrane. (i) Long-term stability of the SGO-W/PES membrane at 2.0 bar. The separation performance showed a small fluctuation over 3 days and ultrasonic treatment five times. A, B, C and D were reprinted with permission from ref.95, ref.96, ref.97, and ref.98, respectively.

membranes can be fully utilized to obtain fast water transport. Moreover, the whole layer on the surface of the GO NF

membrane can act as a protective coating to increase the stability in water.

Jin et al. prepared hydrophilic polymer layer on the GO membrane, and found that the polymer layer can efficiently improve the mechanical stability of the GO membrane (**Fig.10A**).⁹⁵ Zhao et al. reported a structurally durable rGO NF membrane coated with carbon nanotube (CNT). The CNT protective layer cross-linked by polyvinyl alcohol and succinic acid can endow the GO membrane with high-pressure (at least 1bar) back-flushing (**Fig.10B**).⁹⁶ In fact, besides stability, the protective coating can also provide other benefits such as anti-fouling and easy regeneration,⁹⁶ making it a potential way to fabricate high-performance GO NF membranes. Lou et al. prepared a sandwich-structured GO NF membrane via electrospinning/electrospinning method, and found that the GO NF membrane coated with polyamide nanofiber networks can keep stable even under ultrasonication (**Fig.10C**).⁹⁷ Most recently, Li et al. reported that the out-of-plane swelling and interlayer-spacing expansion of GO membranes in water can be suppressed bilaterally by the porous coats and hollow fiber substrates (**Fig.10D**).⁹⁸

3.2 Improving the interfacial stability between the GO layer and substrates

Another instability problem is that GO membranes easily peel off the underlying substrate due to the insufficient interfacial adhesion between the GO layer and substrate,⁶³ which severely limits its practical application. Surface modification of the substrates is an effective way to improve the interfacial interaction between substrates and GO nanosheets. For example, the modification of ceramic support by saline can improve the interfacial adhesion with GO layer.⁹⁹ Morelos-Gomez et al. utilized polysulfone membrane coated with

polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as substrate to improve the interface interaction, and found that the obtained GO membrane achieved a steady performance for up to 120h under intense cross-flow with the help of the PVA intermediate layer (**Fig.11A**).⁷⁷ Jin et al. designed aldehyde (glutaraldehyde or maleic anhydride)-modified chitosan (O=CS), with a moderate molecular weight and abundant functional groups, as the interfacial long-chain molecular bridge,⁶³ and found that the O=CS can offer sufficient physical and chemical interactions between the substrates and GO layer, avoiding the peeling off of GO layer from substrates even under a harsh water separation process (**Fig.11B**).⁶³

Considering the diversity of substrates for supporting GO membrane, it is necessary to develop a universal method to realize the surface modification of various substrates. Mussel-inspired adhesive materials such as polydopamine (PDA), tannic acid, and other polyphenol can form coatings with active groups on almost any substrates' surfaces, making these coatings become a powerful tool for surface modification.^{6, 100-112} Thanks to the high adhesive ability of PDA, GO nanosheets can be attracted and firmly bound to the surface of substrates surface, remarkably enhancing the stability of the GO membrane (**Fig.12**).¹¹³⁻¹¹⁵

It should be noted that GO membranes on ceramic hollow fiber substrates are unstable at the dry state, mainly due to the drying-related shrinkage (**Fig.13A**).⁴² Li et al. demonstrate that GO hollow fiber membrane can be stabilised by using a porous poly(methyl methacrylate) sacrificial layer, which creates a space between the GO membrane and substrate thus allowing stress-free shrinkage (**Fig.13B**).¹¹⁶

Fig.11 (A) GO/FLG membrane preparation.⁷⁷ (a) Porous polysulfone substrate, PVA coating on the substrate (blue), the GO/FLG solution is deposited by spray-coating, the composite membrane with the GO and FLG sheets oriented parallel to the surface. (b) Photographs of GO/FLG membranes without and with PVA as an intermediate layer after 60 min under cross flows of 400 and 1,000 ml min⁻¹ at 1 MPa for 1 h. PVA considerably improves membrane adhesion, as seen on the images under a cross-flow of 1,000 ml min⁻¹. The white arrow indicates the area where peel-off begins. (B) Nanofiltration performance of GO-PDA/O=CS/ceramic membrane.⁶³ (a) Photos of GO/ceramic, GO-PDA/ceramic, and GO-PDA/O=CS/ceramic membranes after high-power sonication for 30 min in water. Cross-sectional SEM images of (b) GO-PDA/O=CS/nylon and (c) GO-PDA/O=CS/MCE membranes. MCE: mixed-cellulose acetate. Insets are photographs of each membrane. (d) Photograph of scaled inner surface GO-PDA/O=CS/ceramic membrane with 40 cm length. A and B were reprinted with permission from ref.77 and ref.63, respectively.

Fig. 12 (A) Highly stable GO membrane based on PDA functionalized supports.¹¹³ (a) Schematic diagram of the synthesis of GO membranes on the PDA-modified α - Al_2O_3 supports through vacuum filtration method. (b) FESEM images of the GO membrane prepared on a PDA-modified Al_2O_3 disk. (c) Ion rejection and water flux of the GO membrane prepared on PDA-modified Al_2O_3 disk as a function of the operation temperature for desalination of 3.5 wt% seawater by pervaporation. (B) Photographs of the GO membrane prepared on (a) the non-modified and (b) PDA-modified α - Al_2O_3 disks as a function of placing time in air at 25 °C.¹¹³ A and B were reprinted with permission from ref.113.

Most recently, B. Kaner et al. developed a novel thin-film lift-off (T-FLO) technique that enables the fabrication of robust GO membranes (Fig. 14A).¹¹⁷ In detail, the active layer GO is cast on a glass pane, and the thickness and chemistry of GO selective layer can be facily tuned during this casting process. Then a fiber-reinforced, epoxy-based resin is cured on top of the GO layer to form a covalently bound support layer. After submersion in water, the cured membrane lifts off from the substrates, obtaining a robust, freestanding, asymmetric GO composite membrane.¹¹⁷ Compared with common scenario such as deposition of a GO film by filtering a GO suspension on substrates, the T-FLO method results in much strong adhesion between GO membrane and substrates.¹¹⁸ As a result, the obtained T-FLO-GO membrane can keep stable in water for at least 30 days (Fig. 14B), and exhibits stable separation performance under different pressures and long-time operation.¹¹⁸

4. Challenges and perspective

Although significant progresses have been made on improving the stability of GO NF membranes in aqueous environment,

Fig. 13 (A) Drying-related shrinkage of GO membrane on supports.⁴² (a) Photographs of (a) a GO membrane supported by a PES polymeric filter, and (b) a GO membrane supported by an alumina hollow fiber. (B) Sacrificial layer stabilised GO membranes.¹¹⁶ (a) A scheme of the working principle of the use of sacrificial layer to stabilise GO membrane on a hollow fibre substrate. (b) The whole view of the cross section of a yttrium stabilised zirconia (YSZ) hollow fibre. (c) An SEM image showing the GO/PMMA/YSZ tri-layer structure, where the sacrificial PMMA layer is sandwiched in the middle by the top GO layer and the bottom YSZ substrate. (Scale bar=200 nm in the smaller image) (d) An SEM image showing the GO/YSZ structure after the PMMA layer was washed by acetone. (e) The results of gas tightness tests of the GO/YSZ hollow fibre membrane prepared with a sacrificial layer. (f) The result of repeated N_2 gas permeation tests of a dry GO/YSZ hollow fibre membrane without using a sacrificial layer. (g) The result of a long term stability test with O_2 on a 150 nm-thick sacrificial layer stabilised GO/YSZ hollow fibre. A and B were reprinted with permission from ref.42 and ref.116, respectively.

there are still some challenges for the commercial application of GO NF membranes.

Firstly, the long-term stability of GO NF membrane is still a major concern. The testing time for the stability of GO membranes are only from several hours to a few months, which is far below the duration for practical application. So the long-term stability of the GO NF membranes should be further investigated.

Secondly, the GO NF membranes should be resistant to back washing and chemical cleaning, since these operations are usually applied to resolve membrane fouling. However, GO membranes that can withstand back washing and chemical cleaning are still scarce.

Fig. 14 (A) GO NF membranes based on thin-film lift off (T-FLO).¹¹⁷ (a) Fabrication of thin-film lift off (T-FLO) membranes. The thin-film interference pattern created by a several-hundred-nanometers-thick active layer can be seen in the top right photograph. (b) Schematic of a nanostructured graphene oxide (T-FLO-GO) composite membrane.¹¹⁸ Common scenario: the deposition of a GO film by filtering a GO suspension onto a substrate (minimum adhesion in the composite structure). This work: post-polymerizing an epoxy layer with percolating porous structure onto a GO nanofilm results in strong adhesion within the composite structure. (B) Mechanically robust T-FLO-GO membranes.¹¹⁸ a) Photo of a control in water for 3 days. The control was air-dried before being placed into water. (b) Photo of a T-FLO-GO membrane immersed in water for 30 days. (c) Photo of a bent T-FLO-GO membrane with a 32-nm-thick GO layer and a 9:1 diamine ratio epoxy. A and B were reprinted with permission from ref.117 and ref.118, respectively.

Thirdly, the stable precise separation of GO NF membranes in water is still a challenge. It has been reported that GO membrane can be reduced to rGO after certain operation conditions.^{119, 120} The reduction of some GO nanosheets during operation will change the d-spacing, leading to the unstable nano channels, which is bad for the precise separation. Besides, the size of nano channels in water may also be changed by the operation pressure.^{121, 122}

Fourthly, as far as we know, the effects of physical properties such as surface wrinkles and lateral width of GO nanosheets on the stability of GO membrane in aqueous environment are rarely reported.^{123, 124} Correspondingly, facile and scalable methods for fabrication of GO nanosheets with controllable surface wrinkles and lateral width are also need to be developed.

In brief, more researches are needed to endow the GO NF membrane with excellent stability while keep the high permeation flux and precise separation performance of the membrane.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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The stability of graphene oxide (GO) nanofiltration (NF) membrane in aqueous environment: Progress and challenges

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The progress and challenges for the stability of graphene oxide nanofiltration membrane in aqueous environment have been reviewed and prospected.

